

Financial Technology Revolution: Transforming Banking Operations in Sub-Saharan Africa

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Abstract:

Across Sub-Saharan Africa, technological revolution, particularly in the financial sector through mobile money, is restyling banking operations. The study examined the revolutionary effect of mobile money, a critical financial technology (FinTech) innovation, on traditional banking services in Sub-Saharan Africa. It contributed to the enduring discussion on whether mobile money threatens or boons traditional banking institutions, highlighting the study's significance and employing the robust PMG-ARDL panel model to assess the extent of the interplay between mobile money and banking operations. The annualised time series data from the decomposed Sub-Saharan African countries were also employed to evaluate the extent of the interplay between mobile money influence and banking operations from 2011 to 2022. The findings shed light on the extent of FinTech's influence in reshaping banking operations and increasing financial inclusion in the region. A 1% change in mobile money services through active mobile money accounts and the value of transactions reduces reliance on traditional banking operations in the long run. Mobile money technology has a substitutional and complementary influence on regional and sub-region banking operations. Mobile money offers convenient, cost-effective, and flexible services. These findings align with the technology acceptance models and provide valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders to embrace synergies to foster trust in secure mobile money transactions. Traditional banking services increase financial inclusion. Address defies arising from the disruptive nature of FinTech.

Keywords: mobile money; banking operation; financial development; Sub-Saharan Africa.

JEL classification: G21; G20; O1; O40; I32

1. INTRODUCTION

The advent of financial technology (FinTech) after the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), characterised by sweeping innovation in robotics, the Internet of Things (IoT), and Artificial Intelligence (AI), progressively restyled the operational and business functionalities of the traditional financial system and industries to enhance efficiency and foster inclusive banking operations globally (Udo, et, al, 2023; Schwab, 2016). The revolutionisation of digital technology and integration into the financial sector in Africa to extend financial services and products to the over 350 million financially excluded adults, notably the Base of the Pyramid (BoP), has shown a distinctive trajectory reflecting unique challenges and its immense growth potential. FinTech, according to the Financial Stability Board (2017), is the integration of technological innovation into financial services to enhance efficiency and create new business models and processes that significantly influence financial service provision (Udo et al.,2023a).

Mobile money (MM) is a convenient, flexible, cost-effective, accessible, and innovative digital financial service channel reliant on mobile phones and network infrastructure. It allows end-users to conduct peer-to-peer remittances, pay bills, save money, manage their finances, and do other things. The transformative impact of MM in the Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) financial landscape is evident in the region's emergence as a global leader in mobile finance services, accounting for 1.6 billion (+13% year-on-year growth rate) in MM services, 763 million active register account (+48% global share), and 401 million monthly active account (+13% year-on-year growth rate); the transactional value of USD 1.26 trillion (+22% year-on-year growth rate) with daily transaction of USD 3.5billion, 7.2 million active agents (+25% year-on-year growth rate) (GSMA, 2023).

The 59% increase in financial inclusion in 2022 from 43% reported in 2017 and the astonishing growth and dominance of MM in SSA can be attributed to the comprehensive mobile communication infrastructure coverage to facilitate MM accessibility and checkmate barriers associated with traditional banking infrastructure (Siano et al., 2020). FinTech disruption of traditional banking services through MM has set the phase for financial liberalisation and inclusive growth in SSA countries. The findings of Naghavi (2019) and Siano et al. (2020) acknowledge the contributive impact of regulatory consistency in facilitating the establishment and adoption of mobile money services in the sector. The desirability of MM is spurred by its several benefits, as highlighted by Ahmad et al. (2020), Adaba et al. (2019), Chukwumah and Islam (2017); Udo et al. (2023a); Udo et al. (2023b) include reduction in transaction costs, access to liquidity and empowerment of the unbanked population through private savings ownership, convenience, affordability and others. Despite the extensive adoption of MM across SSA, variations in adoption, growth and usage patterns persist across the region (See Table 1).

Table 1 Mobile Money Growth Rate Across Sub-Regional SSA

Sub-Regions	Live Service	Register Account	Active 30-day Accounts	Transaction Volume	Transaction Value
Easter Africa	56	390m (12%)	115m (8%)	28bn (18%)	492bn (23%)
Western Africa	66	290m (27%)	76m (30%)	12bn (29%)	277bn (22%)
Central Africa	18	65m (6%)	22m (9%)	3.7bn (20%)	58bn (10%)
Southern Africa	14	18 (16%)	4.7 (24%)	490m (28%)	5.2bn (14%)

Note: values in parentheses represent the percentage change.

Source: Author compilation from GSMA (2023) Data:

Table 1 shows mobile money growth rates across SSA sub-regions and disparities in adoption and utilization. Western and Eastern Africa demonstrate robust adoption rates and transaction volumes, signifying dominance, while Central and Southern Africa lag in registered accounts, active accounts, and transaction volumes. The dominance of West and East Africa in the mobile money services industry is attributed to specific countries' growth rates. Nigeria in West Africa, with an estimated population of 200million, operate one of the most extensive mobile money services with operators such as MTN Mobile Money, Paga, Palmpay, Opay, monipoint and others in Ghana MTN Mobile Money, Vodafone Cash, and AirtelTigo, considerably contribute to the region's dominance. In Eastern Africa, M-Pesa, operated by Safaricom in Kenya and Vodacom M-Pesa, Tigo Pesa, and Airtel Money in Tanzania and Uganda, also contribute to the region's dominance.

The interoperability between mobile money usage and traditional banks is ignited by users' convenience, accessibility, cost-effective, and flexibility, acknowledged in the findings of Dunne and Kasekende (2018), Ky et al. (2019), Lv et al. (2022), which in recent times sparked concerns on the potential threat to stability and development of the traditional financial institutions. Bank operations denote the breadth and depth enhancement to offer comprehensive, convenient, accessible, cost-effective and flexible financial services. Contemporary studies of Eilu and Auma (2017); Dunne and Kasekende (2018); Ky et al. (2019); Lv et al. (2022); Ndwiga (2020); Nguena (2020); Safiullah and Paramati (2022) and Udo, et, al (2023) assessing FinTech focused on the effect on economic growth, financial inclusion, stability, monetary policy. Studies exploring the FinTech revolution and the transformative effect on bank operations through mobile money are limited in SSA, and FinTech's potential unpremeditated and disrupting impact on bank funding, lending behaviour, and financial stability remains relatively unexplored in SSA countries; this study sought to address this knowledge gap.

Financial inclusion emphasises linking the unbanked and underbanked individuals, businesses, and households to the mainstream flexible, accessible and affordable financial services (Sosu, 2019; Siddik et al., 2019; Udo et, al 2023). Voluntary exclusion embraces decisions not to adopt financial services due to a lack of urgent need, cultural and religious persuasions, and involuntary exclusion ignited by poverty, income inequality, burdensome documentation for formal account opening, market failures, bank concentration, and free market flaws decrease

financial inclusion in SSA countries and regions. Mobile money's adoption and usage anchors on maintaining an active mobile account with mobile money service providers and the astonishing growth and dominance, particularly in countries like Nigeria, Ghana, Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda and Senegal, emphasises economic, financial, and social stability (IFC, 2022) (See Table 2).

Table 2: Account ownership at a financial institution or with a mobile money service provider (% of population ages 15+)

Years	SSA Countries	Nigeria	Ghana	Kenya	Tanzania	Uganda	Senegal
2011	23.33	29.67	29.43	42.34	17.26	20.46	5.82
2014	34.27	44.44	40.51	74.66	39.78	44.45	15.42
2017	42.63	39.67	57.72	81.57	46.75	59.2	42.34
2021	55.07	45.32	68.23	79.2	52.43	65.91	55.96

Source: Author compilation from World Bank (2023)

The implications of this growth on the banking sector development remain largely unexplored from an empirical standpoint, which therefore necessitates further studies. To address this gap, the study objective is to assess the transformative influence of the mobile money revolution on SSA banking operations. By evaluating the banking operations, this study seeks to reveal the extent of the transformative impact of mobile money on the mainstream banking system and contribute remarkably to the discourse and facilitating informed decision-making in the region's economic ecosystem. The theoretical and empirical literature on the transformative contribution of the mobile money revolution on banking operations and development are critically reviewed in the next section.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Globally, the transformative impact of FinTech on the traditional system has been a remarkable subject of discourse. The empirical literature of Buchak et al. (2021) and Zhu and Lu (2021) revealed that the transformative effect results from its cost-effectiveness, innovative product offerings, changing consumer preferences, and regulatory environment. Previous studies on FinTech focused on deposit markets, with limited attention on mobile money, a subset of FinTech that plays a significant role in enhancing financial inclusion and reshaping banking operations and development. The discussion of the broader implications is contentious.

2.1 Theoretical Review

The transformative impact of mobile money on bank operations in SSA is underpinned by the Technology Acceptance Models (TAMs), which provide theoretical insights into individual and organizational adoption of FinTech, specifically mobile money services and factors driving its services adoption, utilisation and impact on traditional banking operations. Davis, in 1989, proposed the TAMs, arguing that technological products and acceptance are influenced by their perceived usefulness and ease of use.

Advancing the frontiers of TAMs, Venkatesh et al. (2003) developed the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model, incorporating additional factors such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions as the fulcrum for acceptance and adoption of technological innovation. Performance expectancy reflects an individual's or organisation's conviction that technology enhances performance. In the context of FinTech, mobile money users perceive it as a more efficient and convenient way to access financial services, make transactions, and manage their finances.

Expectancy signifies perceived ease of use associated with mobile money services to encourage adoption among individuals and ease the cumbersome process associated with traditional banking services. Social influence, characterised by societal norms and pressure associated with adopting and accepting mobile money services within communities, compels individuals to adopt these services to align with social expectations and standards. Facilitating conditions refer to infrastructural support such as mobile networks, smartphones, agent networks, and regulatory frameworks available to enable mobile money services. In the context of SSA, mobile money adoption aligns with factors outlined in TAM models. Siano et al. (2020) attribute mobile money adoption to the growth of mobile infrastructure. Chukwumah and Islam (2017) emphasise convenience, reduced access time, transport costs, and enhanced mobile money services as critical drivers.

From a societal perspective, mobile money provides flexible, convenient and liquidity access to the unbanked, underbanked and financially excluded populace, generically rebranded as the "Base of the Pyramid (BoP)"

(Udoh et al., 2018). In the context of banking operations, this study expands the frontiers of the TAM theoretical framework by proposing that a unit increase in mobile money usage, facilitated by convenience, accessibility, and affordability, has both substitution and complementary effects on banking operations.

The substitution effect revealed that sustained mobile money usage will gradually replace conventional banking services such as ATMs, bank branches and bank accounts. The substitution effect stems from the convenience and ease of use offered by mobile money platforms, which decrease the reliance on complex traditional banking channels. The complementary effect of mobile money usage reshapes banking operations through interoperability to enhance the connectivity and accessibility of financial services by integrating diverse systems and platforms to work together seamlessly. This study aims to validate or refute the proposed theory on mobile money's substitution and complementary effects on banking operations.

2.2 Empirical Review

The empirical studies assessing mobile money primarily focused on economic growth and financial development. The findings of this study reflect the diverse impact of mobile money on various aspects of financial development. Studies conducted by Lehmann-Uchner and Menkhoff (2020) on mobile money's influence on economic growth across Africa revealed that insufficient network coverage and financial illiteracy negatively influence mobile money usage and the level of financial service demanded relative to the number of registered mobile money accounts. The study was critiqued for generalising its conclusions solely on observations from a country, thereby restricting the applicability of the findings to a broader context.

In Africa, Ahmad et al. (2020) assessed the impact of mobile money on financial inclusion and observed that a 1% rise in mobile money usage reduces financial exclusion. The study was critiqued for its narrow focus on financial inclusion as the sole measure of financial development. Exploring the FinTech and economic growth nexus in Nigeria (Udo et al., 2023) utilised the ARDL model, direct measures of FinTech and unbundled financial inclusion indicators. Findings revealed that automated teller machines negatively influence economic growth and financial inclusion due to infrastructural deficits, high maintenance costs, and security concerns. Web pay, mobile banking, and point of sale enhance financial inclusion.

Examining mobile money's influence on livelihoods, Donovan (2012) assessed the contributive impact of M-Pesa, a leading mobile money service provider across six countries. He observed that the positive effects on livelihoods did not increase demand for other financial services as a result of regulatory restrictions. The findings provided an in-depth insight into the mobile money effect that can be applied to a broader context. Lashitew et al. (2019) delve into disparities in mobile money's impact on financial inclusion across countries using the regression model and attribute the disparities to institutional, economic and regulatory variables. These findings are corroborated by the studies of Della Peruta (2018) and Gasperin et al. (2019), reporting a positive mobile money and financial inclusion nexus. Empirical assessment conducted by Nantege (2015), Severino and Tonderai (2015), and Nyakwana (2016) underscored the disruptive influence of mobile money on traditional banking institutions. Empirical consensus on the extent of this disruption remains elusive.

Mobile Money and Bank Development Nexus

Empirical investigations into the correlation of mobile money and banking operations have been a focal point in contemporary research; delving into the dynamic interplay to elucidate the transformative impact of mobile money on the banking sector's evolution is the primary objective of this study.

Banking operations within the financial development context refers to the enhancement of the banking sector's capacity to perform its financial intermediation functions within an economy (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Čihák et al., 2013; Aluko & Ajayi, 2018). This improvement, according to Mhadhbi et al. (2017), embraces various facets such as the banking sector deepening, operational and business enhancements for efficiency, and the accessibility to banking services by the banked, underbanked and unbanked (Mhadhbi et al., 2017). The dominance of bank-based financial development indicators in SSA countries reflects a relatively nascent stock market (Tembo and Makina, 2020; Udo et al., 2023b). The variation in banking operations in SSA anchors on the extent of economic growth, proposing a bi-directional causality between the two (Bist & Bista, 2018; Udo et al., 2019). Asongu and Odhiambo (2019) accredited the disparities to educational level, intelligence, and cognitive ability, which indicate a positive link between higher levels of these factors and a greater appreciation for financial markets. Kodila-Tedika et al. (2017) observed that geographical location influences banking operations; landlocked countries and those closer to the

equator exhibit lower levels of bank development. Additionally, institutional quality significantly shaped the operational and business activities of the banking sector (La Porta et al., 1997; La Porta, 1999). Feeble investor protection laws and derisory legal enforcement erode investors' confidence.

Extant literature has largely ignored the impact of FinTech innovations, particularly mobile money, on banking operations in SSA. Mobile money was adopted as a direct measure of FinTech as a result of the upsurge in mobile network frontiers in rural areas. Extant studies limit FinTech indicators to classical bank indicators, neglecting banking evolution beyond classical financial borders. Mobile money services, Internet banking, point-of-sale, web pay, and other retail digital financial platforms control a substantial percentage of financial services' access, usage, and penetration. Telecommunications mobile networks and firms sustain them.

Studies exploring the mobile money nexus credit availability or macroeconomic implications for banking operations. Beck et al. (2015) assessed the nexus of mobile money and credit availability and focused only on the short-term dynamics. Using the partial least squares model, Alhassan and Koaudio (2019) examined the macroeconomic effects of mobile money. It observed a positive nexus between mobile money, economic growth, and private-sector credit. However, the findings of these studies fail to address its contribution to changes in banks' physical infrastructure and asset allocation. Rouse and Verhoef (2017) offered divergent perspectives on whether mobile money threatens or supports traditional banks. While capturing the impact of mobile money on banking infrastructure, Rouse and Verhoef (2017) nosedived in capturing the effect on banks' total assets, credit and bank accounts.

Pelletier et al. (2020) noted that mobile money facilitated banking sector development; as such, the spillover effects are more remarkable when banks offer it. Munalye (2015) observed that mobile money adoption positively influences retail banking operations through an increase in their clientele base as interoperability of the mobile money platforms and banking system enables banks to capture users active on mobile money platform. These studies lack comprehensive investigations into the broader impact of mobile money on the banking model, including changes to infrastructure and financial assets, and also ignore the temporal dimension of the nexus.

This study contributes to the literature by examining the transformative influence of mobile money evolution on banking operations in SSA countries. Mobile money was adopted over other retail digital financial platforms for its affordability, flexibility, convenience, and accessibility. It relies on mobile phone network infrastructure, which is more extensive than internet coverage in developing regions. Mobile money bridges large cash-based informal economic SSA regions for stress-free cash-in and cash-out transactions using phone features, whereas internet banking requires smartphones and internet access. The wider reach, accessible technology, and diverse features of mobile money make it a significant driver of financial inclusion in overcoming hurdles associated with internet access, bank branch availability, and affordability.

By adopting a time-based perspective, dynamic PGM-ARDL model and employing the direct measures of banking operations, the study seeks to provide a deeper understanding of the region's evolving long and short –run financial landscape and depart from previous literature focused on financial inclusion using the regression model. The extensive use of the regression analytical models by Ndubuisi (2017), Akinwale (2018), and Nwakobi et al. (2019) question the rationality of their findings. Gunst and Mason (1980) noted that inferences based on a single model are statistically suspicious, and the embrace of a varied model will provide vital policy formulations on mobile money evolution in banking operations in SSA countries (Grassa & Gazdar 2014; Udo et al., 2023). The following section explains the methodology adopted for the study.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the *ex-post facto* research design and utilises data collated from the GSMA database, the World Bank's Global Financial Development Database, World Governance Indicators mobile and UNCTAD from 2011 to 2022. The base year 2011 was adopted as the starting point for GSMA data on mobile money in SSA countries.

1. FinTech proxied by mobile money (MM) is measured by:
 - i. Active mobile money accounts (AMM) and
 - ii. Value of mobile money transactions (VMM).
2. Bank operations (BAO) = the unbundled dimensions of (availability, penetration, and usage) denoting:
 - i. Number of bank branches per 100,000 adults (BB = Availability): Access and transaction availability are fundamental to financial inclusion.

- ii. Number of bank accounts per 1000 adults (BAC= Penetration): An all-inclusive financial system requires deep penetration (Nguyen, 2020; Udo et al, 2023).
- iii. ATMs per 100,000 adults (ATM =Usage): An all-inclusive financial system ensures the full utilisation of financial services.

Internet access (% of the population) (INA) and mobile cellular subscriptions (per 100 people) (MCS) were adopted as control variables for their contributions to shaping MM usage and banking operations in SSA countries. Access to the INA increases individuals', businesses', and households' connection to digital financial platforms, including mobile banking apps and mobile money services in SSA, where traditional banking infrastructure also exists. MCSs are the primary channel for mobile money transactions in SSA countries. The widespread adoption of mobile phones enabled individuals, even in rural areas, to access mobile money services where traditional banking infrastructure is deficient. The proliferation of mobile phones in SSA has led to a surge in mobile money usage. The panel consisted of four regions in SSA: Eastern Africa (12 countries), Central Africa (7 Countries), Southern Africa (9 countries), and Western Africa (20 Countries) (See Table 3).

Table 3: Sample Countries

Panel: Angola, Burundi, Central African Republic, Chad, Congo, Democratic Republic of Congo, Republic of Rwanda, Comoros, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Madagascar, Mauritius, Seychelles, Somalia, South Sudan, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Botswana, Eswatini, Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Benin, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Cote d'Ivoire, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Gambia, The, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Sao Tome and Principe, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo.
Eastern Africa: Comoros, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Madagascar, Mauritius, Seychelles, Somalia, South Sudan, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda
Central Africa: Angola, Burundi, Central African Republic, Chad, Congo, Democratic Republic of Congo, Republic of Rwanda
Southern Africa: Botswana, Eswatini, Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe
Western Africa: Benin, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Cote d'Ivoire, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Gambia, The, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Sao Tome and Principe, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo

Source: Author's Compilation (2024)

3.2 Model Specification

The Pooled Mean Group (PMG) panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model proposed by Pesaran et al. (1999) was adopted for its robust framework to handle a mix of I(0) and I(1) variables, assess the long and short run MM and bank operations nexus in SSA, account for variations across regions, address endogeneity, outlier concerns, challenge of heterogeneous slopes by generating consistent means of short-run coefficients while maintaining homogenous long-run coefficients. The model assumption of homogeneity in long-run coefficients is not without bias if the slopes are indeed heterogeneous. The PMG-ARDL model is well-suited for small cointegrated samples, thus aligning with the study's objectives to uncover MM usage's short- and long-term impact on banking operations. The model was specified linearly as follows:

$$BAO_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MM_{it} + \beta_2 INA_{it} + \beta_3 MCS_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (Eq 1)$$

Where: ε_{it} = Error term, i = cross section and t = period.

$$\ln BAO_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln BAO_{t-1} + \beta_2 \ln MM_{t-1} + \beta_3 \ln INA_{t-1} + \beta_4 \ln MCS_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^a a_1 D \ln(BAO_{t-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^a a_2 D \ln(MM_{t-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^a a_3 D \ln(INA_{t-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^a a_4 D \ln(MCS_{t-1}) + \varepsilon_{it} \dots (Eq 2)$$

Where: D = first difference operator; $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = long-run coefficients; β_0 = constant; $a_1 - a_4$ = short-run coefficient; a = lag and ε_{it} = error term. BAO = Bank Development, MM = Mobile Money Services, INA = Internet access (% of the population) and MCS = Mobile cellular subscriptions (per 100 people). The presence of long-run co-integration in (eq 1) paves the way for the estimation of the panel error correction model (ECM) specified as:

$$D(\ln BAO_{it}) = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^a a_1 D \ln(BAO_{t-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^a a_2 D \ln(MM_{t-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^a a_3 D \ln(INA_{t-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^a a_4 D \ln(MCS_{t-1}) + \lambda ECT_{it-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (Eq 3)$$

Where: ECT = error correction term; λ = the speed of adjustment of the variables from short run to long run equilibrium.

Before the model estimation, the preliminary tests, including the cross-sectional dependence tests conducted using the Breusch-Pagan LM (Breusch & Pagan, 1980), Pesaran Scaled LM (Pesaran, 2004), and the Pesaran CD (Pesaran, 2004) tests. Studies neglecting the cross-sectional test are likely to produce spurious results due to globalization and integration. The CD model was specific as $CD = \sqrt{\left(\frac{2T}{N(N-1)}\right) \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} (p_{ij})} N(0, 1) \dots\dots\dots(Eq 4)$

Where P_{ij} = the pairwise correlation. N = the sample, T = time
 The unit root tests were conducted using the (first-generation IPS and second-generation CIPS). The CADF and CIPS equations are expressed as:

$$\Delta Y_{it} = \beta_1 + p_i Y_{it-1} + \beta_{iy_{it-1}} + \sum_{j=0}^k Y_{ij} \Delta y_{it-1} + \sum_{j=0}^k Y_{ij} \delta y_{it-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(Eq5)$$

$$CIPS = \left(\frac{1}{N}\right) \sum_{j=1}^k t_i(N, T) \dots\dots\dots(Eq6)$$

Where: β_1 = deterministic term k lag order, y_t = cross-sectional mean of time t .
 Given that the hypothesis of homogeneity between the long-run parameters cannot be assumed, the Hausman (1978) test was performed to determine the most appropriate estimator under the null hypothesis of homogeneity between Pooled Mean Group (PMG), Mean Group (MG) and Dynamic fixed effect (DFE).

MG and PMG are not significantly different.

H₀: PMG is more efficient

H₁: PMG is not efficient

Decision Rule:

Use PMG if p-value is > 0.05 (**H₀** Accept)

Use MG if MG p-value is < 0.05 (**H₀** Reject)

a. EMPIRICAL ESTIMATION

The empirical findings of this study start from the descriptive statistics and unit root tests before the model estimations.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics

Sub-Saharan Countries	BAC	ATM	MCS	BB	VMM	AMM	INA
Mean	0.789	48.548	4.287	31.113	625479.	1755.44	25.66
Median	0.249	21.513	2.481	23.868	370.42	806.88	22.67
Maximum	10.35	322.71	103.33	176.78	6.7209	1984.72	84.34
Minimum	0.000	0.0092	18.917	2.857	0.038	99.757	3.243
Std. Dev.	1.564	68.380	7.952	24.478	2.050	2436.17	12.91
Skewness	3.641	2.242	5.935	2.708	32.741	3.219	1.527
Kurtosis	16.85	7.395	55.320	11.872	1073.00	16.58	5.809
Prob...	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.0000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Central Africa	BAC	ATM	MCS	BB	VMM	AMM	INA
Mean	0.136	54.106	4.744	27.060	1195.95	542.905	20.88
Maximum	0.536	97.164	103.33	176.788	31558.9	3188.75	61.225
Minimum	0.000	21.200	4.845	2.857	1.8041	99.757	3.2430
Std. Dev.	0.09	20.50	9.40	24.45	3480.82	336.33	8.94
Skewness	1.47	-0.03	6.31	3.68	6.25	2.76	1.28
Kurtosis	5.566	2.068	53.306	18.177	46.22	16.50	6.061
Prob..	0.000	0.658	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Southern Africa	BAC	ATM	MCS	BB	VMM	AMM	INA
Mean	0.533	14.273	3.689	29.315	161615	1532.64	27.27
Maximum	1.387	44.057	42.092	151.54	6.7209	5101.9	72.717
Minimum	0.075	1.348	18.917	10.587	0.0383	253.38	8.0894
Std. Dev.	0.290	9.548	6.249	17.166	3.3008	933.309	12.72

Skewness	0.71	1.07	2.752	2.88	20.322	1.28	1.35
Kurtosis	2.735	3.44	15.59	14.20	414.00	4.55	4.819
Prob..	0.000	0.0014	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Western Africa	BAC	ATM	MCS	BB	VMM	AMM	INA
Mean	61.594	94.216	51.24	49.711	196.51	6717.21	90.599
Maximum	97.250	322.711	142.42	160.05	732.39	1984.7	144.66
Minimum	19.00	0.0092	2.148	5.735	4.624	948.22	42.258
Std. Dev.	25.552	94.471	43.82	32.652	261.35	3428.53	23.01
Skewness	-0.170	0.876	0.525	0.805	0.796	1.510	-0.206
Kurtosis	1.757	2.471	1.801	3.606	1.779	6.212	2.479
Prob...	0.0127	0.011	0.0015	0.0187	0.006	0.000	0.297
Eastern Africa	BAC	ATM	MCS	BB	VMM	AMM	INA
Mean	7.0365	5.3950	3.2477	6.2026	10.548	5740.736	1394.075
Maximum	10.091	10.352	6.9493	8.3420	13.175	24140.6	31338.8
Minimum	3.1699	1.5413	0.3370	3.0784	6.9343	23.806	4.6707
Std. Dev.	2.2600	1.7834	1.7982	1.5084	1.9971	7790.61	5488.18
Skewness	-0.1980	0.0529	0.2541	-0.2147	-0.3765	1.1783	5.3152
Kurtosis	1.7383	3.7679	2.3782	2.1649	1.8862	2.9538	29.513
Probability	0.3116	0.6699	0.6593	0.6925	0.2997	0.0246	0.0000

Sources: Author (2024)

In SSA countries, the mean of BAC per capita (0.789) indicates restricted access to formal banking services, and the median value of 0.249 revealed a skewed distribution, suggesting that a significant portion of the population in SSA countries lacks access to formal banking services, which negatively impact on financial inclusion and economic growth. The mean value of 48.548 for the number of ATMs per capita and the skewed value of 2.242 indicates disparities in ATM availability ignited by unequal access to essential banking services and financial transactions, particularly in rural or underserved areas.

The mean number of MCS per 100 people is 4.287, indicating relatively widespread mobile phone usage, with mobile phones serving as a gateway to financial inclusion and enabling individuals to conduct transactions remotely. The mean value of 31.113 for BB per capita indicates moderate accessibility to physical banking infrastructure. The kurtosis value of 11.872 indicates disparities in the availability of bank branches across SSA countries, affecting individuals' access to in-person banking services. The mean value of 1755.44 for AMM indicates significant penetration of MM services. The substantial reliance on MM services in SSA countries is due to the convenience and accessibility offered by the platform, particularly to underserved populations. The skewed and kurtosis values (3.219 and 16.58) indicate disparities in AMM.

The mean percentage value 25.66 for INA accessibility indicates that limited INA access in SSA countries impedes individuals' access to online banking services and information necessary for economic empowerment. The skewness value 1.527 suggests a moderately skewed distribution of internet access percentages across countries. The mean value 625,479 for VMM indicates substantial reliance on MM services for financial transactions. The high skewness and kurtosis values (32.741 and 1073.00) indicate a high VMM transaction across countries.

At the sub-regional level, the low mean values for BAC (0.136) and INA (20.88%) in central Africa signify restricted financial inclusion and digital connectivity. The relatively high skewness and kurtosis values indicate unequal distribution and disparities in the region's MCS and MM usage. In Southern Africa, the moderate mean values for BAC (0.533) and INA (27.27%) indicate improved financial and digital inclusion compared to Central Africa. The skewness and kurtosis in MM transactions indicate uneven adoption and usage across the region. In Western Africa, the mean values for BAC (61.594) and INA (90.599%) reflect relatively robust financial inclusion and digital connectivity, supported by skewness and kurtosis. The ATM availability and MM usage disparities suggest uneven development within the region. In Eastern Africa, mean values for BAC (7.0365) and INA (1394.075%) indicate growth, and the skewness and kurtosis value for INA indicate disparities in digital connectivity, which may hinder the full potential of MM. Understanding regional disparities is crucial for designing effective strategies to promote financial inclusion and economic growth in SSA.

4.2 Cross-sectional Dependence Tests

Globalisation and interconnectedness of countries imply that nations and regions are vulnerable to standard policies and shocks of global events. Neglecting the cross-sectional dependent test in panel data showing cross-sectional dependence will lead to spurious results. The test was conducted using the Pesaran CD test (Pesaran, 2004).

Null Hypothesis

$H_0: \alpha = 1$, there is no correlation of the residuals (error term).

$H_1: \alpha \neq 1$, there is a correlation of the residuals (error term).

Table 5 Cross-Sectional Dependence

	Panel SSA		Southern Africa		Central Africa		Eastern Africa		Western Africa	
	CD- Test	Prob	CD-Test	Prob	CD-Test	Prob	CD-Test	Prob	CD-Test	Prob
BAC	41.19***	0.000	16.69***	0.000	19.76***	0.000	20.52***	0.000	12.94***	0.000
ATM	40.12***	0.000	17.18***	0.000	22.80***	0.000	6.28***	0.000	42.65***	0.000
MCS	30.78***	0.000	3.27***	0.001	23.78***	0.000	9.77***	0.000	16.77***	0.000
BB	68.52***	0.000	4.91***	0.000	22.91***	0.000	21.33***	0.000	8.37***	0.000
VMM	80.53***	0.001	10.96***	0.000	23.10***	0.000	8.12***	0.000	5.59***	0.000
AMM	35.82***	0.000	4.05***	0.001	2.29*	0.022	6.87***	0.00	51.86***	0.000
INA	16.49***	0.000	9.59***	0.000	21.98***	0.000	1.81*	0.062	1.200*	0.22

Note: ***, **, * denote significance levels of $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$, and $p < 0.1\%$ respectively.

Source: Author's construct (2024).

The null hypothesis of cross-sectional independence is overruled at both panel and country-specific levels at 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. This implies that countries are not utterly independent from each other due to vulnerabilities to standard policies and shocks. The second-generation unit root test was adopted to test the series' stationarity properties for a robust analysis.

4.3 Unit Root Test

Table 6 Stationarity Tests

Constant and Trend										
CIPS										
	Southern Africa		Central Africa		Eastern Africa		Western Africa		Panel	
	I (0)	I (1)	I (0)	I (1)	I (0)	I (1)	I (0)	I (1)	I (0)	I (1)
BAC	-5.34***	-6.87***	-3.81***	-5.81***	0.231	-4.58***	-1.566	-3.90***	-5.61***	-3.466
ATM	-4.89***	-6.12***	-4.87***	-6.48***	-	-6.81***	-01.34	-3.98***	-7.23***	-4.04***
MCS	-4.91***	-7.01***	-2.32***	-3.98***	-2.87	-4.85***	-4.01***	-5.54***	-6.51***	-4.51***
BB	-5.90***	-8.76***	-4.81***	-6.15***	-2.89	-4.14***	-3.78***	-4.69***	-6.01***	-4.84***
VMM	-3.23***	-6.71***	-3.58***	-5.70**	-	-4.03***	-4.81***	-5.90***	-5.03***	-4.21***
AMM	-1.74	-4.38***	-4.80***	-6.12***	-	-5.91***	-3.70***	-5.50***	-7.62***	-4.50***
INA	-3.50***	-5.65***	-5.10***	-7.92***	-	-5.51**	-3.82***	4.67***	-4.32**	-5.02***
CADF										
BAC	-2.98***	-4.89***	-2.38***	-4.01***	-	-6.012***	-0.08	-6.02***	-5.21***	-4.85***

ATM	-3.09***	-4.89***	-3.99***	-4.03***	-3.01** *	-5.031***	-1.82	-5.31***	-6.23***	-5.21***
MCS	-3.98***	-6.91***	-3.48***	-4.01***	-2.91** *	-6.012***	-2.01***	-6.12***	-7.11***	-3.76***
BB	-3.88**	-5.40***	-3.08***	-5.92***	-3.08** *	-4.925***	-0.021	-4.95***	-5.92***	-4.28***
VMM	-2.05**	-5.81***	-3.25***	-4.90***	-3.01** *	-4.902***	-3.05***	-5.92***	-6.13***	-4.66***
AMM	-1.91	-4.81***	-3.71**	-3.51***	-4.01** *	-4.512***	-4.01***	-6.12***	-6.36***	-6.36***
INA	-0.21	-4.56***	-0.01	-3.06***	-3.01** *	-4.069***	-3.01***	-3.69***	-6.26***	-6.921***

***Critical values of CIPS for 0.01% significance level is -2.250, -3.510, -2.130; CADF 0.01% significance level is -2.012, -1.958, -2.001.

Source: Author's (2024).

Before estimating the long-run nexus, the constant and trend unit root models were conducted to confirm the integration order of the series for a robust analysis. The results reported in Table 4 showed that the series are integrated of order I(1) and I(0) for both CIP and CIPS. The test result gives credibility to the PGM/ARDL estimation model irrespective of the order of integration but not with the I(2) series. The Hausman (1978) test model confirmed the PMG estimator to be more efficient than the MG estimator at a p-value of <0.05% (0.771, 0.492, 0.699, 0.5123, 0.542) for the panel and sub-regional SSA countries to address heterogeneity and interdependence concerns.

PMG-ARDL Model Estimation

Active mobile money (AMM) accounts and value of mobile money transactions (VMM) measures FinTech proxied by mobile money (MM).

Bank operations and development are proxied by:

1. Number of Bank Branches per 100,000 adults (BB) (Availability)
2. Number of bank accounts per 1000 adults (BAC) (Penetration)
3. ATMs are available per 100,000 adults (ATMs) (Usage):

Control Variables

1. Internet access (% of the population) (INA)
2. Mobile cellular subscriptions (per 100 people) (MCS).

PMG Estimation for Active Mobile Money

The PMG estimations focus on the long-run and short-run link between indicators of banking operations and MM indicators of AMM and VMM across SSA and its sub-regions.

Table 6 PMG Estimation for Active Mobile Money

Panel A: Long Run Equation									
	Panel SSA			Southern Africa			Central Africa		
Variables	BB	ATM	BAC	BB	ATM	BAC	BB	ATM	BAC
Dimensions	Availability	Usage	Penetration	Availability	Usage	Penetration	Availability	Usage	Penetration

AMM	-0.740 (-11.421) **	-3.348 (-7.836) **	-0.864 (-5.342) **	-0.763 (-13.279) **	-0.560 (4.28)	-0.927 (-11.329)	0.257 (8.246)	0.107 (6.916)	-0.468 (-4.649)
MCS	0.350 (15.44) **	10.491 (9.435) **	0.240 (5.079) **	0.905 (2.739)	-0.118 (-3.117)	0.623 (2.892)	-0.880 (-6.088)	0.387 (3.762)	0.071 (2.967)
INA	0.673 (6.408) **	0.533 (4.188) **	-0.160 (-0.657)	-0.028 (-1.349)	0.131 (2.422)	3.170 (1.104)	0.510 (7.452)	0.896 (5.118)	0.196 (6.212)
Panel B: Short-Run Equation									
CointEq(-1)*	-0.907 (-20.392)	-0.513 (-6.151)	-0.707 (-15.898)	-0.618 (-7.87)	-0.607 (-13.650)	-0.987 (-9.449)	-0.784 (-17.437)	-0.3045 (-6.203)	-0.738 (-6.028) **
	Eastern Africa			Western Africa					
Variables	BB	ATM	BAC	BB	ATM	BAC			
Dimensions	Availability	Usage	Penetration	Availability	Usage	Penetration			
AMM	0.809 (6.707)	0.072 (0.914)	0.902 (8.963)	-0.993 (-7.602)	-0.813 (7.668)	0.713 (6.731)			
MCS	-0.872 (8.665)	0.402 (2.11)	0.700 (5.359)	-0.813 (7.66)	0.213 (2.011)	0.283 (2.676)			
INA	0.572 (6.312)	0.502 (0.716)	0.501 (3.836)	0.713 (1.010)	0.820 (7.739)	0.883 (8.333)			
Panel B: Short-Run Equation									
CointEq(-1)*	-0.781 (-6.375)	-0.701 (-12.325)	-0.501 (-6.519)	-0.823 (-10.706)	-0.701 (-9.120)	-0.78 (-9.827)			

Source: Authors (2024)

Panel and cross-region PGM-ARDL findings on the nexus between AMM and bank operations (BAO) indicators of ATM, BB and BAC reported in Table 6 show that across the sub-regions, a 1% increase in AMM positively influences BAO in the long run indicates that MM services play a substantial role in improving financial inclusion through access (BB), usage (ATM) and penetration (BAC). The results across the regions align with the notion that MM is a gateway to financial inclusion, particularly in SSA, due to banking infrastructure deficits—the positive coefficients of INA influence BAO due to prevalent internet connectivity. The short-run equation captures the immediate effects of changes in the variables on BAO. The CointEq(-1) values signify the short-run speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium. From the results, BB will take one year and one month to converge to long-run equilibrium, while ATM and BAC will take one year, ten months, and one year and four months, respectively.

Discussion

Panel: MM proxied by AMM, in the long run, significantly and positively impacts BAO proxied by BB, ATM, and BAC in SSA. AMM enhances banking services and financial inclusion by 74% through BB. Beck et al. (2007) argued that AMM indicates a growing demand for financial services, leading to the opening of new branches to cater for this demand. In the long run, accessibility, affordability, and flexibility offered by MM platforms contribute to financial inclusion. Mobile phone networks diminish bank concentration in urban areas, the cumbersome bank account opening process, the rigorous process of renewing or collecting new ATM cards and high ATM operational costs in SSA by 3.3% and 86%. The hassle-free nature of MM transactions reduces reliance on traditional banking methods. In this context, AMM is considered convenient, cost-effective, and flexible when conducting financial transactions and improving financial inclusion. The positive contribution of MCS and INA facilitates the adoption and usage of MM services. The studies of Cull et al. (2016), Glennie et al. (2016) and Aker and Mbiti (2010) corroborate the findings of this study. Cull et al. (2016) revealed that security concerns associated with MM may barricade adoption. Hence, trust in secure MM transactions and supportive government regulations is crucial in expanding the frontiers of MM services in SSA.

At the regional level: In Southern Africa, a 1% decrease in BB, BAC and ATM, respectively, increases AMM availability, usage and penetration by 76% for BB, 93% for BAC and 56% for ATMs. The AMM increase is accredited to social norms, peer influence, cost-effectiveness, income levels, education, and urbanisation, bridging the financial inclusion gap left by traditional banking systems. The positive coefficients of MCS and INA facilitate access

to financial services and enhance adoption rates. The CointEq(-1) is correctly signed negative and significant. ECM values of (-0.618; -0.607; 0.987) confirm the long-run convergence speed from short-run divergence influenced by the regulatory framework, technological advancements and consumer behaviours by 61%, 60% and 98%, respectively, per annum. These findings highlight the transformative overlook of MM in improving financial activities in Southern Africa. By leveraging MCS and INA, stakeholders promote the widespread adoption of MM services, driving economic growth and development in the region.

Central Africa exhibits mixed results; AMM positively influences BB by 25% and ATMs by 10%, but negatively on BAC by 46%. This suggests a nuanced link in the region, possibly influenced by specific market dynamics ignited by limited physical infrastructure (ATM and BB), high transaction costs, lack of trust in digital financial services, cultural norms, regulatory barriers, and individual preferences. MCS negatively impacts BB by 88% but affects ATM positively by 38% and BAC by 71%. INA shows mixed results, with a negative impact on BB and a positive impact on ATM and BAC. The mixed results are traced to market dynamics, regulatory environments, and cultural factors. The negative influence on ATMs and BB implies challenges in integrating MM with traditional banking services. The ECM values of (-0.784; -0.3045; 0.738) confirm the long-run nexus and speed of convergence from short-run divergence to long-run equilibrium per annum. The findings showcase a dynamic environment where MM fosters financial inclusion while potentially disrupting traditional banking models.

In Eastern Africa, the results show a positive nexus across all variables, indicating a complementary nexus where AMM is the gateway to financial inclusion in the region. AMM positively impacts BB by 80% and BAC by 92% but non-significantly on ATM by 0.07%. The non-significant effects on ATMs indicate that traditional banking channels are still relevant in the region. Integrating MM services with ATM networks could enhance usage, penetration and access to banking services. A 1% rise in MCS decreases BB by 87% and positively impacts ATMs by 42% and BAC by 70%. This implies that mobile phone ownership facilitates access to mobile money for transactions, and users leverage the internet for online banking, potentially managing accounts and initiating transactions remotely. Investment in telecommunications infrastructure expands internet reach and user comfort with online banking.

The TAM and UTAUT theories support the findings of these studies. The short-run equation shows the instantaneous impacts of changes in MM factors on banking operations. ECM values of (-0.78; -0.71; 0.50) confirm the long-run nexus and speed of convergence from short-run divergence in the banking sector as it adapts to evolving MM dynamics to long-run, respectively, at 78%, 71% and 50% per annum. The result is a successful co-existence between MM and traditional banking.

In Western Africa the results show that AMM negatively impact BB by 0.99 and ATM by 0.813 and positively on BAC by 0.713. These results indicate a potential substitution effect due to the convenience and accessibility offered by MM to reduce reliance on BB and ATMs. MCS negatively impact BB by 0.813 and positively affect BAC by 0.283 and ATM by 0.231. The results imply that mobile phone ownership is the first step to access to MM services. Internet access improves banking services across various channels, and the negative impact of MM on BB and ATMs shows that MM services offer seamless transactions and broader service offerings than traditional banking channels. The short-run equation shows changes in MM on banking operations. ECM values of (-0.78; -0.71; 0.50) confirm the long-run nexus and speed of convergence from short-run divergence in the banking sector as it adapts to evolving MM dynamics to long-run equilibrium, respectively, at 82%, 71% and 78% per annum.

The variations across sub-regions and the findings underline the transformative role of FinTech through the MM revolution in shaping banking operations across SSA. The diversity in the results is accredited to market dynamics in specific regions, infrastructure limitations (physical branches, ATMs), and user preference. Trust in digital services and regulatory environment. Theoretically, perceived usefulness, ease of use, and attitudes vis-à-vis technology acceptance influence the acceptance of MM and MCS. The negative impact on ATMs indicates concerns about infrastructure limitations or regulatory barriers associated with integrating MM with traditional banking services.

PMG Estimation for Value of Mobile Money Transactions

Table 7 shows the long and short-run estimation between mobile money proxied by the value of mobile money transactions and bank development indicators.

Table 7 PMG Estimation for Value of mobile money transactions

Panel A: Long Run Equation									
	Panel SSA			Southern Africa			Central Africa		
Variables	BB	ATM	BAC	BB	ATM	BAC	BB	ATM	BAC
Dimensions	Availability	Usage	Penetration	Availability	Usage	Penetration	Availability	Usage	Penetration
VMM	-0.706 (-6.878)	-0.216 (-2.107)	-0.811 (-7.901)	0.893 (8.703)	-0.179 (-4.177)	-0.801 (-5.776)	0.362 (13.240)	-0.707 (-6.587)	0.717 (9.705)
MCS	0.576 (5.612)	0.727 (7.083)	-0.551 (-5.369)	0.938 (9.135)	-0.879 (-6.338)	0.708 (9.591)	0.226 (8.266)	0.507 (6.867)	0.777 (4.468)
INA	0.776 (7.560)	0.901 (8.777)	0.357 (3.480)	0.321 (3.133)	0.779 (5.618)	0.692 (6.449)	0.326 (2.562)	0.110 (0.143)	0.835 (11.302)
Panel B: Short-Run Equation									
CointEq(-1)*	-0.976	-0.376	-0.674	-0.832	-0.663	-0.563	-0.611	-0.768	-0.832
	Eastern Africa			Western Africa					
Variables	BB	ATM	BAC	BB	ATM	BAC			
Dimensions	Availability	Usage	Penetration	Availability	Usage	Penetration			
VMM	-0.706 (-7.044)	0.392 (2.091)	0.282 (7.466)	-0.699 (-8.871)	-0.479 (-4.747)	0.731 (7.245)			
MCS	0.816 (7.950)	0.602 (6.859)	-0.209 (-5.539)	0.219 (11.641)	2.700 (8.741)	0.271 (8.773)			
INA	0.081 (6.433)	0.829 (4.412)	0.709 (8.998)	0.207 (2.060)	0.291 (9.421)	0.310 (9.744)			
Panel B: Short-Run Equation									
CointEq(-1)*	-0.921	-0.463	-0.762	-0.881	-0.231	-0.651			

Sources: Author (2024)

The estimations reported in Table have the value of mobile money transactions as the primary explanatory variables on bank development indicators employed in the study.

In the panel, a 1% rise in the value of mobile money transactions (VMM) decreases BB by 70%, ATM usage by 21% and BAC by 81%, respectively, reflecting a gradual shift from traditional banking infrastructure in SSA due to high operational cost to a convenient, affordable and accessible MM service. TAM and UTAUT theories support user preference for technologies perceived as convenient, cost-effective and accessible. Studies by Glennie et al. (2016), Udo et al. (2023), and Demirgüç-Kunt et al. (2015) confirm MM's cost-effective transaction and ease of use, making financial services more accessible to low-income populations and those without formal identification compared to traditional banking systems.

Mobile cellular subscription (MCS) and Internet access (INA) increase the frontiers of banking services to reduce reliance on traditional banking models. TAMs and UTAUT theories support these results, emphasising the significance of perceived usefulness and ease of use in technology adoption. ECM values of (-0.976; -0.376; 0.674) confirm the long-run nexus and the speed of convergence from short-run divergence to long-run equilibrium, respectively, at 97%, 37% and 67% per annum.

At the sub-regional level: In Southern Africa, a 1% rise in VMM significantly increased BB by 89%. A 1% decrease in ATMs and BAC increases VMM by 17% and 80%, respectively, in the long run. The increase in BB denotes a shift in customer preferences to mobile banking to reduced reliance on traditional brick-and-mortar infrastructure and practices. The decline in ATMs inferred a transition to digital banking channels, which challenges traditional ATM-based services. The increase in BB indicates financial inclusion improvement, especially in a region with limited access to traditional banking services. The study findings align with TAMs and UTAUT theories on technology adoption for convenience. Socioeconomic factors, regulatory environments, and technological infrastructure also influence the adoption. Similarly, security concerns, regulatory barriers, and infrastructure limitations hinder mobile money adoption and its impact on banking operations. The ECM values of (-0.832; -0.663;

0.563) confirm the long-run nexus and the speed of convergence from short-run divergence to long-run equilibrium, respectively, at 83%, 66% and 56% per annum.

In Central Africa, a 1% change in the value of VMM boosts BB by 36% BAC by 71% and reduces ATM usage by 70%, indicating a positive contribution to financial services expansion and a shift from reliance on physical infrastructure to mobile and digital banking solutions. The study of Ngomsu et al. (2020) supports these findings, arguing that MM services expedite financial services to areas with high financial exclusion rates. The findings of Amankwah-Amoah et al. (2019) stress the role of technology adoption and innovation in driving financial inclusion in Africa. ECM values of (-0.611; -0.76; -0.83) confirm the long-run nexus and convergence speed from short-run divergence to long-run equilibrium, respectively, at 61%, 76% and 83% per annum. These results highlight the resilience and adaptability of the banking ecosystem in Central Africa.

In Eastern Africa, the significant decline in banking operations (BAO) highlights the growing dominance of VMM by 70%, reflecting a substantial shift towards MM services from traditional banking services. This shift is accredited to convenience, accessibility, and trust in MM platforms. Muto et al. (2018) and Udo et al. (2023b) acknowledged the convenience and accessibility features of mobile money platforms as critical drivers of adoption in African markets. The positive coefficient for MCS across the variables (0.392, 0.602, and -0.209) indicates that consumers embrace technologies perceived as convenient and beneficial to their needs and daily operational and business activities. The positive coefficient for INA supports these results along with the findings of Hughes et al. (2019) and the TAMs and UTAUT theories, arguing that the ease of use and usefulness of MM platforms influence individuals' adoption and sustained usage over traditional banking systems. ECM values of (-0.921; -0.463; -0.762) confirm the long-run nexus and the speed of convergence from short-run divergence to long-run equilibrium, respectively, at 92%, 46% and 76% per annum.

In Western Africa, the coefficient of VMM across the variables (-0.699, -0.479, and 0.731) indicates nuanced influences; the decline in BB and ATMs correlates with a 69% and 47% shift in consumer preferences and regulatory dynamics towards MM services. Donou-Adonsou et al. (2020) observed that the transformative impact of regulatory reforms and technological innovations is evidenced in the restyled African financial landscape to encourage the adoption of MM services over traditional banking channels. Regardless of the upsurge in mobile transactions, Udo et al. (2019) argued that limited access to mobile technology or digital literacy will exacerbate financial exclusion among the BoPs. The positive MCS coefficient for all three variables (0.219, 2.700, and 0.271) and the coefficient for INA across the variables (0.207, 0.291, and 0.310) indicates INA penetrations and MCS in areas without mobile technology or digital literacy for inclusive financing. Mas et al. (2016) argued that user experience and convenience impact MM adoption and increase acceptability among the BoPs in developing regions. Armiya'u et al. (2019) noted that MM penetration and usage in Western Africa is accredited to its cost-effectiveness. Theoretically, TAMs and UTAUT support these findings. MM captures the banked, unbanked and underbanked populations relying on traditional banking services.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study explores the intricate nexus between MM proxied AMM and VMM and the diverse indicators of BAO in SSA and sub-SSA regions. The study findings from the dynamic PMG-ARDL model estimation reveal a nuanced link between the study variables. In the long run, MM indicators in the panel SSA and sub-regions individually impact BAO indicators. Thus signifying a shift in consumer preferences to convenience, cost-effectiveness, and accessible financial services offered by MM. In Central Africa, limited physical infrastructure, high transaction costs, and cultural barriers hinder MM. In Eastern Africa, MM impacts BAO, significantly promoting financial inclusion. Investment in telecommunications infrastructure and user convenience drives MM adoption. The result from Western Africa revealed a potential substitution effect, with MM negatively influencing traditional banking services and infrastructure. These findings indicate a shift to the convenience and accessibility offered by MM platforms due to high traditional banking operational costs. The study findings align with TAMs and UTAUT's theoretical argument on both substitution and complementary effects of MM on BAO. MCS and INA showed varying long-run influence. As such, investments in telecommunications infrastructure and internet accessibility are crucial for expanding the frontiers of MM services in the region to the BoPs.

The study findings offer several actionable policy implications. Stakeholders and regulators in SSA and sub-regional financial institutions should focus on crafting supportive regulatory frameworks to foster trust in secure MM and promote consumer adoption, considering the acceptance of MM services after the COVID-19 pandemic. In the same context, there is a need for integration between MM services and traditional banking channels, especially in regions where MM negatively impacts ATM usage to enhance the overall banking experience, drive financial

inclusion, and ensure there is no marginalization due to security concerns in rural areas where access to financial services is already compromised. In summary, the study findings show opportunities for banks to leverage the interoperability of mobile platforms to expand financial services to the BoPs.

The study's contribution to the extant literature lies in its inclusive analysis of the transformative influence of MM services on banking operations across SSA, and sub-regions post the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR). Assessing sub-regional dynamics, which previous studies ignore, sheds light on factors contributing to the dominance of MM in specific regions and offers nuanced insights into the socio-economic and regulatory dynamics shaping mobile financial services adoption. The introduction of the concept of interoperability between MM platforms and traditional banks and its potential impact on the stability and development of conventional financial institutions adds depth to the understanding of how FinTech disruptions influence broader financial sector development. The study recommends further study to focus on the socio-economic factors influencing mobile money adoption and usage patterns across different regions within SSA.

References:

- Adaba, G. B., Ayong, D. A., & Abbott, P. (2019). Exploring the contribution of mobile money to well-being from a capability perspective. *The Electronic Journal on Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 85(4), e12079. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/isd2.12079>
- Ahmad, A. H., Green, C., & Jiang, F. (2020). Mobile Money, Financial Inclusion and Development: A Review Concerning African Experience. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 34(4), 753-792. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/joes.12372>
- Aker & Mbiti (2010): Mobile phone ownership influences mobile money adoption.
- Aker, J. C., & Mbiti, I. M. (2010). *Mobile payments and the digital divide: Differences in cellphone ownership and use among people experiencing poverty in Kenya*. Digital Divide Network.
- Akinwale, S. O. (2018). Bank Lending Rate and Economic Growth. Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*, 7, 111-122. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJAREMS/v7-i3/4440>
- Alhassan, T. F., & Koaudio, A. J. (2019). Mobile money development in sub-Saharan Africa: Its macroeconomic effects and role in financing development. *International Scientific and Practical Conference on Digital Economy (ISCDE 2019)*, Institute of Digital Economics, Chelyabinsk, Russia (pp. 31–35). Atlantis Press.
- Alhassan, T. F., & Koaudio, A. J. (2019). Mobile money development in sub-Saharan Africa: Its macroeconomic effects and role in financing development. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 105, 314-318. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2991/iscde-19.2019.60>
- Aluko, O. A., & Ajayi, M. A. (2018). Determinants of banking sector development: Evidence from Sub-Saharan African countries. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 18(2), 122-139. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.bir.2017.11.002>
- Asongu, S. A., & Odhiambo, N. M. (2019). Governance, capital flight and industrialisation in Africa. *Journal of Economic Structures*, 8(36), 1-22. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s40008-019-0170-2>
- Beck, T., Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Klapper, L. (2007). *Financial inclusion and economic development*. The World Bank.
- Beck, T., Pamuk, H., Ramrattan, R., & Uras, B. (2015). Mobile Money, Trade Credit and Economic Development: Theory and Evidence. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2588392>
- Bist, J. P., & Bista, N. B. (2018). Finance–Growth Nexus in Nepal: An Application of the ARDL Approach in the Presence of Structural Breaks. *Vikalpa*, 43(4), 236-249. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0256090918813211>
- Breusch, T. S., & Pagan, A. R. (1980). The Lagrange Multiplier Test and its Applications to Model Specification in Econometrics. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 47(1), 239-253. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/2297111>
- Buchak, G., Hu, J., & Wei, S. J. (2021). FinTech as a financial liberator. *NBER Working Paper*, w29448.
- Chukwumah, S., & Islam, N. (2017). Adoption of mobile banking service in rural Nigeria. *Turku School of Economics*.
- Čihák, M., Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Feyen, E., & Levine, R. (2013). Financial Development in 205 Economies, 1960 to 2010. *Journal of Financial Perspectives*, 1(2), 17-36. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3386/w18946>
- Cull, R., Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Morduch, J. (2016). *Mobile banking and financial inclusion: Moving beyond transactions*. *Journal of Development Economics*, 121, 186-202.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *Management Information Systems Quarterly*, 13(3), 319-339. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- Della Peruta, M. (2018). Adoption of mobile money and financial inclusion: a macroeconomic approach through cluster analysis. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 27(2), 154-173. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10438599.2017.1322234>
- Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Klapper, L., Singer, D., & Van Oudheusden, P. (2015). *The global Findex database 2014: Measuring financial inclusion around the world*. The World Bank.

- Donovan, K. (2012). Mobile Money for Financial Inclusion. http://dx.doi.org/10.1596/9780821389911_ch04
- Dunne, J. P., & Kasekende, E. (2018). Financial innovation and money demand: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa. *South African Journal of Economics*, 86(4), 428–448. <https://doi.org/10.1111/saje.12205>
- Eilu, E., & Auma, T. O. (2017). Mobile money services as a Panacea to financial inclusion in sub-Saharan Africa: The case of Uganda. *International Journal of Technology Diffusion*. 8(4), 77–88. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJTD.2017100106Ekanayake>,
- Financial Stability Board. (2017). *Financial stability implications from FinTech: Supervisory and regulatory issues that merit authorities' attention*. Retrieved December 1, 2022, from <https://www.fsb.org/wp-content/uploads/R270617.pdf>
- Gasperin, D., C., R., V., & Stanca, L. (2019). Mobile Money and the Labor Market: Evidence from Developing Countries. SSRN Electronic Journal. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3360234>
- Glennie, W., Kendall, G., & Townsend, R. (2016). *Digital finance and inclusive development: Demystifying the hype*. CGAP Working Papers, (404).
- GSMA. (2023). *State of the Industry Report on Mobile Money 2023*.
- Hausman, J. (1978). Specification Tests in Econometrics. *Econometrica*, 6(46), 1251-1271.
- IFC. (2022). African Fintech Rises to The Challenge.
- Kodila-Tedika, O., Asongu, S. A., & Cinyabuguma, M. M. (2017). Financial Development and Geographic Isolation: Global Evidence. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10419/173647>
- Ky, S., Rugemintwari, C., & Sauviat, A. (2019). *Is fintech good for bank performance? The case of mobile money in the East African Community* (No. hal- 02155077).
- La Porta, R. (1999). The quality of government. *Journal of Law Economics and Organization*, 15(1), 222-279. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jleo/15.1.222>
- La Porta, R., Lopez-De-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1997). Legal Determinants of External Finance. *The Journal of Finance*, 52(3), 1131-1150. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1997.tb02727.x>
- Lashitew, A. A., van Tulder, R., & Liasse, Y. (2019). Mobile phones for financial inclusion: What explains the diffusion of mobile money innovations? *Research Policy*, 48(5), 1201-1215. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.12.010>
- Lehmann-Uchner, K., & Menkhoff, L. (2020). Mobile Money is Driving Financial Development in Africa. *DIW Weekly Report*, 10(21/22), 253-259.
- Mhadhbi, K., Terzi, C., & Bouchrika, A. (2017). Banking sector development and economic growth developing countries: A bootstrap panel Granger causality analysis. *Empirical Economics*.
- Mothobi, O., & Grzybowski, L. (2017). Infrastructure Deficiencies and Adoption of Mobile Money in Sub-Saharan Africa.
- Naghavi, N. (2019). Sub-Saharan Africa Mobile Money: Diverse Use Cases, Enabling Environment Boost Adoption. *Center for Financial Inclusion*.
- Ndubuisi, P., 2017. An examination of the relationship between financial development and economic growth in Nigeria: Application of multivariate var framework. International Association of African Researchers and Reviewers, 2006-2017. Available from www.afrevjo.net.
- Ndwiga, D. (2020). *The effects of FinTechs on bank market power and risk-taking behaviour in Kenya*. KBA Centre for Research on Financial Markets and Policy Working Paper Series (No. 44).
- Nguena, C. L. (2020). How does fintech innovation matter for bank fragility in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA)? *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 1–38.
- Nguyen, T. T. H. (2020). Measuring financial inclusion: A composite FI index for the developing countries. *Journal of Economics and Development*, 23(1), 77–99. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JED-03-2020-0027>
- Nwakobi, P, C, Oleka, D, C, & Ananwude, A, (2019) Effect of Financial Deepening on Economic Growth in Nigeria: A Time Series Appraisal (1986-2018) (December 12, 2019). Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports, 7(3), 1-9, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3504014>
- Pelletier, A., Khavul, S., & Estrin, S. (2020). Innovations in emerging markets: The case of mobile money. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 29(2), 395-421. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/ICC/DTZ049>
- Pesaran, M. H. (2004). General Diagnostic Tests for Cross Section Dependence in Panels. *IZA Discussion Paper*(1240). <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.572504>
- Pesaran, M. H. (2004). General diagnostic tests for cross-section dependence in panels. The University of Cambridge, Faculty of Economics, Cambridge Working Papers in Economics No. 0435.
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., and Smith, R. P. (1999). Pooled mean group estimation of dynamic heterogeneous panels. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 94(446), 621–634.

- Rouse, M., & Verhoef, y. G. (2017). Mobile banking in Sub-Saharan Africa: setting the way towards financial development. *MPRA Paper*(78006).
- Safiullah, M., & Paramati, S. R. (2022). The impact of FinTech firms on bank financial stability. *Electronic Commerce Research*, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-022-09595-z>
- Schwab, K. (2016). The Fourth Industrial Revolution: what it means and how to respond. *World Economic Forum*.
- Severino, M., & Tonderai, N. (2015). Impact of mobile banking on traditional banking practices in Zimbabwe. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, III(1).
- Siano, A., Raimi, L., Palazzo, M., & Panait, M. C. (2020). Mobile Banking: An Innovative Solution for Increasing Financial Inclusion in Sub-Saharan African Countries: Evidence from Nigeria. *Sustainability (Basel)*, 12(23), 10130. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su122310130>
- Sosu, B. (2019). Mobile money in Ghana: a financial inclusion enabler.
- Tembo, J., & Makina, D. (2020). Regional financial integration and its impact on banking development: Evidence from Southern African Development Community countries. *Business Strategy & Development*, 3(3), 356-368. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/BSD2.101>
- Udo, E. S., Abner, I. P., Ndubuaku, V., Udoh, B., E. & Okoh, J. I. (2023b) Effect of FinTech on Cash Holding: Quarterly Evidence from Nigeria: *The Economics and Finance Letters*, 10 (2) 172-182. DOI: 10.18488/29.v10i2.3407.
- Udo, E. S., Akpan, E. J., Abner, I. P., Idongen, K., & Ndubuaku, V., (2019a) Finance-Led Growth and Growth-Led Finance: Evidence from Nigeria Economic and Financial Sector Development. *Humanities and Social Sciences Letters*, 7 (4) 191-198. DOI: 10.18488/journal.73.2019.74.191.198.
- Udo, S. E., Prince, A. I., Edet, I. V., Manasseh, C. O., Daniel, C. O., Okanya, O. C., Mgbobi, I. C., & Onwumere, J. U. J. (2023). Financial Technology and Economic Growth Nexus: Quarterly Evidence From Nigeria. *Seybold Report Journal*, 18(07), 106-129. <https://doi-ojs.org/10-5110-77-9127/>
- Udoh, E., E. Udo, Abner, I. P, R. Ike, T. Tingir & U. Ibekwe, (2018). Effect of administrative capital expenditure on economic development; an emerging nation outlook. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*, 23(1): 1-17.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *Management Information Systems Quarterly*, 27(3), 425-478. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/30036540>
- World Bank. (2023). Account ownership at a financial institution or with a mobile money service provider (% of population ages 15+). Data.
- Zhu, Y., & Lu, J. (2021). *FinTech and Bank Intermediation– Evidence from the Deposit Market in China*. Available at SSRN 4030108.